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CoPropel

Composite material technology for next-generation Marine Vessel Propellers

<https://linktr.ee/copropel>

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Glossary

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DOA	Description of action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
...	

1. Executive Summary

A COPROPEL logo was designed which reflects the main objectives of the project, which is to work on the composite marine propellers. The logo will be the face of COPROPEL and will be used in project website, social media platforms and newsletters from now on. Additionally, a project specific website is being created, along with a LinkedIn and a Twitter page. A linktree link has been created with a single page with the URLs for the website and all the social media pages. Additionally, the CoPropel internal communication platform has been summarized.

2. Deviations

An extension to the original submission date (originally month 3, which would be end of August 2022) was requested and approved due to the fact that many consortium members were on annual leave during the summer months. The submission date for this deliverable was thus extended to month 4 (end of September 2022).

3. COPROPEL LOGO

A dedicated logo which is the visual identity of the project has been created. The logo is illustrated in Figure 1

Figure 1 COPROPEL logo

4. COPROPEL Website

A project website for COPROPEL is being created and will be maintained by TWI as part of WP6. This website provides public information to potential stakeholders on project aims and successes. All project partners use their social accounts such as Twitter and LinkedIn to post project updates and news to increase visibility under the organization's accounts. In such posts, a link to the project website is also provided/mentioned.

The website URL will be: WWW.Copropele.com will be live on 7th of October 2022

Figure 2 The website for CoPropel

The website consists of six sections as illustrated below:

- Objectives and impact: This section provides a detailed description of the COPROPEL project, the objectives and its impact.
- Services: The main activities that will be developed from the CoPropel consortium are: knowledge, prototype, tooling, access to market, IP generation.
- Consortium: This section lists all parties involved in COPROPEL and a short description of their background and area of expertise, along with a link to their main webpages and Logos.
- Media: This is a section in the website where any reports/newsletters/articles or any other information relating to the project can be found. This is another means of communicating the project activities to a wider audience.

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[Brunel Composites Centre \(BCC\)](#) is delighted to announce its participation as associate partner in the Horizon Europe funded CoPropel project (Grant Agreement Number 101056911) which kicked-off on the 24th of June 2022. The CoPropel project aims to develop ship propellers that are lighter, more energy

Figure 3: Media page on the CoPropel Website

- News: Project updates and news from all partners are listed in this section to keep visitors up to date with the recent developments of the COPROPEL project.
- Contact: The point of contact for the COPROPEL project coordination team, as well as the official project email are listed in this section.

The website will be regularly updated by TWI, who will act as the social media and website manager for the duration of the COPROPEL project.

5. COPROPEL Social media

A LinkedIn account will be created that mirrors information shared on the website to increase visibility and reach a larger audience. The LinkedIn URL is: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/copropel>

Figure 4 LinkedIn URL for CoPropel

A Twitter account will also be created and mirrors information shared on the website to increase visibility and reach a larger audience. The twitter URL is: <https://twitter.com/CoPropel>

Figure 5 Twitter URL for CoPropel

A linktree has also been created with all the links [@CoPropel | Twitter | Linktree](#), with the official website and the social media pages <https://linktr.ee/copropel>.

6. Promotional packs

This section summarizes the multiple multimedia promotional activities that are proposed for the duration of the COPROPEL project. As the first planned activity a COPROPEL brochure will be printed. The tri fold brochure, will be designed to handle three main functions: to inform, publicize and identify. Specifically, it highlights the objectives and impact of the project using a concise and very plain language. The front panel will display the Project Logo along with the partners logos and EU logo. The inner panels will describe:

- the goal of the project focusing on its innovative aspects
- the impact of the developed technology and how it can meet the industrial needs.

Additionally, a project presentation specifically for public dissemination and a poster will be created by TWI. All the promotional materials are expected be ready by M6.

7. CoPropel Internal Communication Platforms

The internal communication of the consortium partners and the associated partners is a crucial action in realising a successful implementation of the CoPropel project. Internal communications, except from emails, are being facilitated by the use of Microsoft Teams and SharePoint. More specifically, a private group was created by UoI in Microsoft Teams where all the members of the consortium have access to discuss, organise meetings and share documents. The group, which is captured in the following image, contains a general channel as well dedicated specific channels for each WP. Each channel is expected to act as a point of discussion for the members throughout the project.

Figure 6. Microsoft Teams private group of CoPropel.

Additionally, this group is linked to a private SharePoint workspace, which is used as the internal repository for CoPropel. The SharePoint workspace, which contains different sections for the following items, can be assessed only by the consortium members, either through the Microsoft Teams group, or by using a regular web browser as can be seen in the following image.

- News
- Documents
- Deliverables register
- Risks register
- Milestones register

- Action list

Figure 7. Access to the SharePoint workspace through a regular web browser.

It is expected that the SharePoint will also be used for organising specific meetings in dedicated pages, whereby all the meeting related items will be kept in a single location, to be easily accessible by the consortium members.

Both the above internal communication channels are considered as tools that enhance the management and communication activities between the consortium members and facilitate the teamwork among people that are located in different countries.